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M/M/1/K Loss and Delay Interdependent Queueing Model with Vacation and Controllable Arrival Rates

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Abstract

Objectives: In this study, we assume that the vacation is taken while there are no consumers in the queue. There are several servicemen who will take the synchronous multiple vacations in the system. **Methods:** Assumed some loss and delay in consumers (Elective and emergency) and solve the steady-state probability equations using recursive approach and acquired some obvious iterative expressions. **Findings:** Carried out some numerical analysis using MATLAB and investigated the movement of $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_0})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_1})$ and $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ through graph. Further, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_0})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_1})$ and $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ increase when J_1 & J_0 increases; decrease when M increases. Additionally, when L increases $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ remains constant and $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{A_1})$, $(\mu - \varepsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ increase. **Novelty:** Expanded the preceding models in this study by including vacations and performing the numerical analysis. Using vacation with controllable arrival rates in an optimal way in order to benefit both the server and the customer will minimise waiting time and provide the most feasible, affordable service to the consumer.

Keywords: Markovian Queueing System; Vacation; Loss and Delay; Finite Capacity; Interdependent Arrival and Service Rates; Varying Arrival Rates; Bivariate Poisson Process

1 Introduction

Jain (1998)⁽¹⁾ examined the finite population loss and delay queueing system without the passing idea in prior work. M. Thiagarajan and A. Srinivasan's analysis of the M/M/c/K loss and delay interdependent queueing model with adjustable arrival rates and no passing was published in Thiagarajan and Srinivasan (2011)⁽²⁾. In actual life, the loss and delay issue happen frequently. This is a development of the M/M/1/K Interdependent Queueing Model with Controllable Arrival Rates and Vacation. S. P. Subhapriya and M. Thiagarajan discuss developments and applications in mathematics. (2022)⁽³⁾.

A "vacation period" is when a server starts performing other uninterrupted work when it is idle. We recommend reading Doshi (1986), Ke et al. (2010) and Shweta Upadhyaya⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾ for an in-depth and extensive examination of vacation queueing

systems. The analysis of an M/M/1/N queue with working breakdowns and vacations was done by B. Deepa and K. Kalidass⁽⁷⁾. There have also been numerous more models that are similar⁽⁸⁾.

In this study, we take into account a server vacation scenario with an M/M/1/K loss and delay queueing model. For different arrival rates and independent service processes, the steady state probabilities are determined, and the average waiting periods for two customer kinds (elective and emergency) are produced. Customers that choose to wait patiently to receive the services they require. However, if an emergency consumer finds the server busy and so lost, they quit the system.

2 Description of the Model

Consider finite capacity, loss and delay and vacation queueing system with following assumptions:

The arrival process and the service process are $\{X_1(t)\}$, $\{X_2(t)\}$ respectively are correlated and follow a bivariate Poisson process given by

$$P[X_1(t) = x_1, X_2(t) = x_2] = \frac{e^{-(\lambda_1 + \mu - \epsilon)t} \sum_{j=0}^{\min(x_1, x_2)} (\epsilon t)^j [(\lambda_1 - \epsilon)t]^{x_1 - j} [(\mu - \epsilon)t]^{x_2 - j}}{j! (x_1 - j)! (x_2 - j)!} \tag{1}$$

Where, $x_1, x_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots; \lambda_{01}, \lambda_{02}, \lambda_{11}, \mu > 0, 0 \leq \epsilon < \min(\lambda_{ij}, \mu)$.

Parameters $\lambda_{01}, \lambda_{02}, \lambda_{11}, \mu$ and ϵ are mean arrival rate of elective consumers when the system is in faster rate of arrivals, mean arrival rate of emergency consumers when the system is in faster rate of arrivals, mean arrival rate of elective consumers when the system is in slower rate of arrivals, mean service rate of consumers of type B and co-variance between arrival and service processes respectively.

$$\lambda_n = \begin{cases} \lambda_{0j}; & 0 \leq n < 1, j = 1, 2 \\ \lambda_{01}; & 1 \leq n \leq R - 1 \\ \lambda_{11}; & r + 1 \leq n \leq K \end{cases}$$

$P_{0,n}$ and $P_{1,n}$ are the probability at vacation and at normal state respectively.

$n=0,1,\dots,r-1,r,r+1,\dots,R-1,R,R+1,\dots,K-1,K$.

3 Steady State Equations

We observe that only $P_{0,n}(0)$ and $P_{1,n}(0)$ exists when $n=0,1,\dots,r-1,r$; $P_{0,n}(0), P_{1,n}(0), P_{0,n}(1)$ and $P_{1,n}(1)$ exists when $n=r+1,r+2,\dots,R-2,R-1$; only $P_{0,n}(1)$ and $P_{1,n}(1)$ exists when $n=R,R+1,\dots,K$. Further $P_{0,n}(0) = P_{1,n}(0) = P_{0,n}(1) = P_{1,n}(1) = 0$ when $n > K$.

$$(\lambda_0 - 2\epsilon)P_{0,0}(0) = (\mu - \epsilon)P_{1,1}(0); \tag{2}$$

$$(\lambda_{01} + v - \epsilon)P_{0,n}(0) = (\lambda_{01} - \epsilon)P_{0,n-1}(0); (1 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{3}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + v - \epsilon)P_{0,r+1}(1) = 0; \tag{4}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + v - \epsilon)P_{0,n}(1) = (\lambda_{11} - \epsilon)P_{0,n-1}(1); (r + 2 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{5}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + v - \epsilon)P_{0,R}(1) = (\lambda_{11} - \epsilon)P_{0,R-1}(1) + (\lambda_{01} - \epsilon)P_{0,R-1}(0) \tag{6}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + v - \epsilon)P_{0,n}(1) = (\lambda_{11} - \epsilon)P_{0,n-1}(1); (R + 1 \leq n \leq K) \tag{7}$$

$$(\lambda_{01} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,n}(0) = (\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon) P_{1,n-1}(0) + (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,n+1}(0) + vP_{0,n}(0); (1 \leq n \leq r - 1) \tag{8}$$

$$(\lambda_{01} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,r}(0) = (\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon) P_{1,r-1}(0) + (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,r+1}(0) + (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,r+1}(1) + vP_{0,r}(0); \tag{9}$$

$$(\lambda_{01} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,n}(0) = (\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon) P_{1,n-1}(0) + (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,n+1}(0) + vP_{0,n}(0); (r + 1 \leq n \leq R - 2) \tag{10}$$

$$(\lambda_{01} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,R-1}(0) = (\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon) P_{1,R-2}(0) + vP_{0,R-1}(0); \tag{11}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,r+1}(1) = (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,r+2}(1) + vP_{0,r+1}(1); \tag{12}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,n}(1) = (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,n+1}(1) + (\lambda_{11} - \varepsilon) P_{1,n-1}(1) + vP_{0,n}(1); (r + 2 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{13}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,R}(1) = (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,R+1}(1) + (\lambda_{11} - \varepsilon) P_{1,R-1}(1) + (\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon) P_{1,R-1}(0) + vP_{0,R}(1); \tag{14}$$

$$(\lambda_{11} + \mu - 2\varepsilon) P_{1,n}(1) = (\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,n+1}(1) + (\lambda_{11} - \varepsilon) P_{1,n-1}(1) + vP_{0,n}(1); (R + 1 \leq n \leq K - 1) \tag{15}$$

$$(\mu - \varepsilon) P_{1,K}(1) = (\lambda_{11} - \varepsilon) P_{1,K-1}(1) + vP_{0,K}(1); \tag{16}$$

Let

$$J_1 = \frac{\lambda_{01} - \varepsilon}{\mu - \varepsilon}, J_2 = \frac{\lambda_{02} - \varepsilon}{\mu - \varepsilon}, L = \frac{\lambda_{11} - \varepsilon}{\mu - \varepsilon}, M = \frac{v}{\mu - \varepsilon}, T = \frac{L}{L + M}$$

$$J_0 = J_1 + J_2 = \frac{\lambda_0 - 2\varepsilon}{\mu - \varepsilon}, \text{ where } \lambda_0 = \lambda_{01} + \lambda_{02} \text{ and } Q = \frac{J_1}{J_1 + L}$$

From Equation (2)

$$P_{1,1}(0) = J_0 P_{0,0}(0) \tag{17}$$

From Equation (3)

$$P_{0,n}(0) = Q^n P_{0,0}(0); (1 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{18}$$

From Equations (4) and (5)

$$P_{0,n}(1) = 0; (r + 1 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{19}$$

From Equation (6)

$$P_{0,R}(1) = \frac{J_1}{L + M} Q^{R-1} P_{0,0}(0) = S P_{0,0}(0) \tag{20}$$

From Equation (7)

$$P_{0,n}(1) = T^{n-R}SP_{0,0}(0); (R + 1 \leq n \leq K) \tag{21}$$

From Equation (8)

$$P_{0,n}(0) = [(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-1)})J_0 - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-2)})MQ - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-3)})MQ^2 - \dots - MQ^{(n-1)}]P_{0,0}(0); (2 \leq n \leq r) \tag{22}$$

From Equation (9)

$$P_{1,r+1}(0) = [(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(r)})J_0 - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(r-1)})MQ - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(r-2)})MQ^2 - \dots - MQ^{(r)}]P_{0,0}(0) - P_{1,r+1}(1); (2 \leq n \leq r) \tag{23}$$

From Equation (10)

$$P_{1,n}(0) = [(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-1)})J_0 - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-2)})MQ - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-3)})MQ^2 - \dots - MQ^{(n-1)}]P_{0,0}(0) - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(n-r-1)})P_{1,r+1}(1); (r + 2 \leq n \leq R - 1) \tag{24}$$

From Equation (11)

$$P_{1,r+1}(1) = \frac{[(1 + J_1) \left\{ \begin{aligned} &[(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-2)})J_0 - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-3)})MQ] \\ &- (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-4)})MQ^2 - \dots - MQ^{(R-2)} \end{aligned} \right\} - J_1 \{ [(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-3)})J_0 - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-4)})MQ - (1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-5)})MQ^2 - \dots - MQ^{(R-3)}] \} - MQ^{(R-1)}]}{(1 + J_1 + \dots + J_1^{(R-r-1)})} P_{0,0}(0) = FP_{0,0}(0) \tag{25}$$

From Equations (12) and (13)

$$P_{1,n}(1) = (1 + L + \dots + L^{(n-r-1)})FP_{0,0}(0); (r + 2 \leq n \leq R) \tag{26}$$

From Equations (14), (15) and (16)

$$P_{1,n}(1) = (B + 1)P_{1,n-1}(1) - BP_{1,n-2}(1) - MP_{0,n-1}(1); (n = R + 1, R + 2, \dots, K) P_{0,0}(0); (R + 1 \leq n \leq K) \tag{27}$$

4 Characteristics of the Model

$$P(0) = \sum_{n=0}^K P_{1,n}(0)$$

P(0) exists only when n=1,2,...r-1,r,r+1,...R-1, we get

$$P(0) = \sum_{n=1}^{R-1} P_{0,n}(0) + \sum_{n=1}^r P_{1,n}(0) + \sum_{n=r+1}^{R-1} P_{1,n}(0) \tag{28}$$

Now,

$$P(1) = \sum_{n=0}^K P_{1,n}(1)$$

P(1) exists only when $n=r+1, r+2, \dots, L$

$$P(1) = \sum_{n=r+1}^K P_{0,n}(1) + \sum_{n=r+1}^R P_{1,n}(1) + \sum_{n=R+1}^K P_{1,n}(1) \tag{29}$$

The system is empty can be calculated from the normalizing condition

$$P(0) + P(1) = 1 \tag{30}$$

The expected waiting time for the consumers of type A when the system is in faster, slower rate of arrivals, consumers of type B when the system is in faster, slower rate of arrivals are given by $E(W_{A_0}), E(W_{A_1}), E(W_{B_0})$ and $E(W_{B_1})$ respectively.

$$E(W_{A_0}) = \frac{1}{\mu - \epsilon} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=1}^r (P_{0,n}(0) + P_{1,n}(0)) + \sum_{n=r+1}^{R-1} (P_{0,n}(0) + P_{1,n}(0)) \right] (n) \right\} \tag{31}$$

$$E(W_{A_1}) = \frac{1}{\mu - \epsilon} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=r+1}^{R-1} (P_{0,n}(1) + P_{1,n}(1)) + \sum_{n=R}^K (P_{0,n}(1) + P_{1,n}(1)) \right] (n) \right\} \tag{32}$$

$$E(W_{B_0}) = \frac{1}{\mu - \epsilon} \left\{ P_{00}(0) + \left[\sum_{n=1}^r (P_{0,n}(0) + P_{1,n}(0)) + \sum_{n=r+1}^{R-1} (P_{0,n}(0) + P_{1,n}(0)) \right] (n+1) \right\} \tag{33}$$

$$E(W_{B_1}) = \frac{1}{\mu - \epsilon} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=r+1}^{R-1} (P_{0,n}(1) + P_{1,n}(1)) + \sum_{n=R}^K (P_{0,n}(1) + P_{1,n}(1)) \right] (n+1) \right\} \tag{34}$$

The difference between the expected waiting time of consumers of type A & B when the system is in faster and slower rate of arrivals are

$$D_0 = E(W_{B_0}) - E(W_{A_0}) \text{ and } D_1 = E(W_{B_1}) - E(W_{A_1}) \text{ respectively}$$

5 Numerical Illustrations

For various values of J_1, J_0, L and M the values of $P_{0,0}(0), P(0), P(1), (\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0}), (\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1}), (\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ and $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ are computed.

Table 1. For single server by assuming $r=5, R=8, K=10$

J_1	J_0	L	M	$P_{0,0}(0)$	$P(0)$	$P(1)$	$(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0})$	$(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1})$	$(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$	$(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$
0.8	1.4	0.4	4	0.0522	0.6441	0.3553	345.76	272.23	359.63	279.03
1.2	1.4	0.4	4	0.0313	0.6268	0.3732	561.01	477.25	581.95	489.18
1.6	1.4	0.4	4	0.0139	0.5073	0.4927	1020.6	1416	1057.4	1451.4
1.8	1.4	0.4	4	0.0089	0.4466	0.5534	1398.9	2476.3	14449.1	2538.2
1.2	1.1	0.3	3.6	0.0622	0.7409	0.2591	333.65	166.67	347.37	170.83
1.2	1.3	0.3	3.6	0.0385	0.6742	0.3258	490.4	338.53	509.03	346.99
1.2	1.4	0.3	3.6	0.0440	0.6829	0.3170	434.31	288.03	451.1	295.24
1.2	1.6	0.3	3.6	0.0288	0.6026	0.3974	585.54	551.7	607.29	565.5
2.5	2	0.5	10	0.0011	0.2655	0.7345	6630	26200	6866.8	26855
2.5	2	0.6	10	0.0010	0.2379	0.7621	6630	30346	6866.8	31105
2.5	2	0.9	10	0.0007	0.1631	0.8360	6630	48285	6866.8	49492
2.5	2	1	10	0.0006	0.1434	0.8566	6630	56569	6866.8	57983
1.3	1	0.8	0.6	0.0231	0.5075	0.4925	613.75	850.86	636.34	872.14
1.3	1	0.8	1.3	0.0355	0.5545	0.4455	437.57	502.14	454.23	514.69
1.3	1	0.8	1.9	0.0441	0.5814	0.4187	369.22	379.71	383.69	389.2
1.3	1	0.8	2.5	0.0513	0.6025	0.3975	328.76	309.87	341.99	317.62

Fig 1. By varying J_1 and keeping other parameters fixed

Fig 2. By varying J_0 and keeping other parameters fixed

Fig 3. By varying L and keeping other parameters fixed

Fig 4. By varying M and keeping other parameters fixed

6 Conclusion

It is observed from the table that

- When J_1 increases and the other parameters are kept fixed, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ and $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ increase.
- When J_0 increases and the other parameters are kept fixed, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ and $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ increase.
- When L increases and the other parameters are kept fixed $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ remains constant and $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ increase.
- When M increases and the other parameters are kept fixed, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_0})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{A_1})$, $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_0})$ and $(\mu - \epsilon)E(W_{B_1})$ decrease.

The model includes the earlier models as particular cases. For example, when $\nu = 0$, this model reduces to the M/M/c/K loss and delay interdependent queueing model with controllable arrival rates and no passing⁽⁵⁾. When λ_0 tends to λ_1 , $\epsilon = 0$ and $\nu = 0$, this model reduces to the Finite population loss and delay queueing system with no passing⁽¹⁾. When λ_0 tends to λ_1 and $\epsilon = 0$, this model reduces to the conventional model.

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